

COMPARISON BETWEEN MODE I INTERLAMINA AND INTRALAMINA FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF THIN UNIDIRECTIONAL GRAPHITE(AS4)/EPOXY(1908) LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In the previous study, the Mode I intralamina fracture toughness test was performed by using the three kinds of thin unidirectional graphite/epoxy laminates, i.e. T300/#3601, T800/#3631 and AS4/1908. The results obtained were that the Mode I intralamina fracture toughness values, $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$, were 183, 420 and 662J/m², respectively.

In the present paper, a method for determining the Mode I interlamina fracture toughness value, $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$, of AS4/1908 laminates which have the highest $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$ value among the above-mentioned materials is discussed, and then the $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$ determined by this method is compared with that of the above $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$. The $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$ is 368J/m² and this value is 45% less than the $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$ of 662J/m².

Keywords: Graphite/epoxy composites, Thin unidirectional laminates,
Interlamina fracture toughness, Intralamina fracture toughness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Generally, the fracture process of the laminate composite materials consists of the initiation and growth of delamination and intralamina cracking with respect to the failure of the weakest part of the interface of interlamina and fiber/matrix, and the final fracture. Their individual growth and mutual coalescence often lead to the fatal failure of the lamination structure. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate these failure quantitatively and to elucidate the influence factors in order to use them as the base structural members. It seems that the research on delamination is many and the research on intralamina cracking is relatively a few, but the research discussed on the relation between delamination and intralamina cracking is much less [1-3].

In the previous study [4], the Mode I intralamina cracking property test was performed in order to evaluate the intralamina fracture behavior and the bridging fiber effect of the three kinds of thin unidirectional graphite/epoxy laminates, i.e., T300/#3601, T800/#3631 and AS4/1908. The study on the intralamina cracking of unidirectional CFRP laminates is the very important subject for the adhesive evaluation of a fiber/resin interface since the intralamina cracking, i.e., the splitting crack, grows along the fiber direction from a bolt hole and a surface damage produced by certain causes etc.. The results obtained were that the Mode I intralamina fracture

toughness values, $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$, of T300/#3601, T800/#3631 and AS4/1908 laminates were 183, 420 and 662J/m², respectively. The difference of these values could be explained through the degree of the bridging fiber effect by analyzing the adhesive force between fiber and resin. In the present paper, a method for determining the Mode I interlamina fracture toughness value, $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$, of the above-mentioned thin unidirectional AS4/1908 laminates is discussed, and then the $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$ determined by this method is compared with that of the previous $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$.

2. ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES

As for the quantitative evaluation parameter of Mode I interlamina fracture property and intralamina one of the previous study, the strain energy release rate, G_I , is used. The G_I value is calculated by using the compliance method and the simplified equations that contain a geometrical non-linearity associated with the large deformation of DCB specimen. The critical strain energy release rate, $(G_I)_c$, based on the compliance method is given by

$$(G_I)_c = \frac{P_c}{2b} \frac{dC}{d\bar{a}} \quad (1)$$

where C , P_c , a and b are the compliance, the load at the initiation of delamination, the delamination length and the specimen width, respectively. The $(G_I)_c$ value calculated by using Equation 1 is denoted as $(G_I)_c(c)$. By assuming the specimen geometry as the cantilever and by using the above-mentioned P_c , a and b , the $(G_I)_c$ based on the simplified equations [5] that contain a geometrical non-linearity associated with the large deformation of DCB specimen can be obtained as follows.

In the case of load P_c , $(G_I)_c$ is given by

$$(G_I)_c = \frac{\bar{d}^2}{9bEI} (4\beta_P + 5\beta_P^2) P_c^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\beta_P = \frac{2}{\left\{ 1 + \sqrt{1 + (48/35) (P_c \bar{d}^2)/(2EI)} \right\}^2}$$

where EI is the flexural rigidity of the cantilever, and in the case of displacement δ_c ,

$$(G_I)_c = \frac{9EI}{4b\bar{d}^4} \left\{ \frac{(4+5\beta_D)}{4\beta_D} + 4\beta_D^2 + 5\beta_D^3 \right\} \delta_c^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\beta_D = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \sqrt[3]{A + \sqrt{A^2 - 1}} + \sqrt[3]{A - \sqrt{A^2 - 1}} \right\}, \quad A = 1 + \frac{243}{35} \frac{\delta_c}{\bar{d}}$$

where δ_c is the load-point-displacement at the initiation of delamination.

The $(G_I)_c$ values calculated by using Equations 2 and 3 are denoted as $(G_I)_c(P)$ and $(G_I)_c(D)$, respectively.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The present material is unidirectional reinforced graphite (AS4)/epoxy (1908, 120°C Hardening type) composite laminates consisting 6 plies that is laminated by the unidirectional prepreg tape of thickness 0.2mm. The mechanical properties of this material is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of AS4/1908 laminates.

Material	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν	Fiber volume (%)
AS4/1908	124.0	9.6	4.7	0.339	62.0

(a) Interlamina test

(b) Intralamina test [4]

Figure 1. Shape and dimension of DCB specimens.

The shape and dimension of DCB specimen with a pre-crack is shown in Figure 1(a). The pre-crack was fabricated by embedding a very thin teflon sheet to 15mm from a free edge at the midplane of 6 plies. Also as to reference, the shape and dimension of the specimen of previous intralamina fracture toughness testing [4] is shown in Figure 1(b).

As for the test conditions, Mode I delamination test was carried out by using the Instron type testing machine (Capacity of loadcell : 50kgf) at the crosshead speed 0.5mm/min in the constant temperature room, whose temperature and humidity are kept at $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $60 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$. The load (P)-displacement (δ) curves are recorded on a X-Y recorder.

The compliances for one DCB specimen are obtained to each stable delamination length of about 10mm by calculating the slopes of P- δ curves until the total delamination length becomes about 100mm. The exact length of each delamination growth is measured from the photograph.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Mode I Delamination Fracture Property

A typical load-displacement curve with the delamination growth is shown in Figure 2. From this figure, it is found that unloading straight line at each delamination length dose not pass through the origin. For this cause, it is considered that as the each DCB specimen aspect of the early and the later period of delamination growth is shown in Figures 3(a) and 3(b), the deformation of DCB specimen is geometrically non-linear with delamination growth. Therefore, the critical strain energy release rate, i.e., interlamina fracture toughness, $(G_I)_c$, is calculated by using the above-mentioned Equations 1, 2 and 3.

Figure 2. Typical load versus displacement curve.

Figure 3. Macroscopic photographs of delamination growth.

Figure 4. Relation between C and a.

Figure 5. Relation between $(G_I)_c(c)$ and a.

Figure 6. Relation between $(G_I)_c(P)$ and a.

First, Figure 4 shows the relation between the compliance, C, obtained from Figure 2 and the delamination length, a, both plotted in logarithms. From the Figure 4, both are in the straight line relation and C is expressed with the exponential function of a. Figure 5 shows the relation between the $(G_I)_c(c)$ value obtained by substituting this relation to Equation 1 and a. $(G_I)_c(c)$ shows a constant value irrespective of a and this value is about 321J/m^2 . On the other hand, the results that a depends on each values of $(G_I)_c(P)$ and $(G_I)_c(D)$ obtained from Equations 2 and 3 are shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively. $(G_I)_c(P)$ increases with increase of a.

Figure 7. Relation between $(G_I)_c(P)$ and a .

Figure 8. Relation between $(G_I)_c(N)$ and a .

As compared with this, $(G_I)_c(D)$ is in tendency to decrease with a . Also, it is found that in the early stage of delamination, $(G_I)_c(D)$ value is higher than $(G_I)_c(P)$ value although both values become to agree with each other over the range where a is almost equal to 50mm. Results of such tendency also are obtained by Suemasu et al. [5] for GFRP composites. Therefore, $(G_I)_c$ which is taken into consideration of a geometrical non-linearity of DCB specimen is obtained from the arithmetic mean of $(G_I)_c(P)$ and $(G_I)_c(D)$ to a . This result is shown in Figure 8. From this figure, it is found that if the each values of the early stage of delamination and the later one are omitted, the $(G_I)_c$ can be considered as a almost constant value with respect to a . This value is about 422J/m² and also is denoted as $(G_I)_c(N)$.

4.2. Determination Of The Mode I Interlamina Fracture Toughness Of The Thin Laminates

For results obtained in the preceding section 4.1, the values of $(G_I)_c(C)$ and $(G_I)_c(N)$ are respectively about 321J/m^2 and 422J/m^2 . The difference between the two values is about 30%. Then, the Figures 4 and 8 are examined again over the each range of delamination length. First, as the large deformation of specimen is not observed from Figure 3(a) in the early period of delamination growth, $(G_I)_c$ obtained from the compliance method could be is considered as a almost true value. Such being the case, we obtain the $(G_I)_c$ of the 30mm neighborhood of delamination length and its value is 358J/m^2 .

Next, as the large deformation of specimen is occurs in the later period of delamination growth as is seen from Figure 3(b), it is considered that $(G_I)_c$ obtained from the simplified equations that contain a geometrical non-linearity is also a true value. Such being the case, we also obtain the $(G_I)_c$ within the delamination length 80–90mm and its value is 378J/m^2 .

Comparing with the above-mentioned two values, it is found that these show comparatively near value. Therefore, as it is considered that the fracture toughness is independent of crack length, the interlamina fracture toughness obtained from the arithmetic mean of 358J/m^2 and 378J/m^2 , $(G_I)_{c(\text{inter})}$, is 368J/m^2 . We determine this value for the Mode I interlamina fracture toughness of this present thin laminates.

4.3. Comparison Between Mode I Interlamina And Intralamina Fracture Toughness

In this section, the interlamina fracture toughness, $(G_I)_{c(\text{inter})}$, obtained in the preceding section 4.2 is compared with the intralamina fracture toughness obtained by the specimen for the previous study shown in Figure 1(b), where the intralamina fracture toughness is denoted by $(G_I)_{c(\text{intra})}$.

Figure 9. comparison between $(G_I)_{c(\text{inter})}$ and $(G_I)_{c(\text{intra})}$ [4].

Figure 9 shows the results of $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$ and $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$ [4]. From this figure, it is found that the $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$ is 45 % lower than $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$.

This result can be explained from the fact that the bridging fiber existed in the previous intralamina fracture test can not be observed and also the morphology of the delamination surfaces due to the SEM observation is a flat pattern.

5. CONCLUSION

In the present paper, a method for determining the Mode I interlamina fracture toughness value, $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$, of thin AS4/1908 laminates which have the highest Mode I intralamina fracture toughness value, $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$, among the materials in the previous paper is discussed, and then the $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$ determined by both the compliance method and the two simplified equation methods is compared with that of the above $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$.

The results obtained are that the $(G_I)_{c(inter)}$ is 368 J/m^2 and this value is 45% less than the $(G_I)_{c(intra)}$ of 662 J/m^2 . It is thought that when if the intralamina fracture toughness that may be influenced in adhesion condition of the fiber/matrix interface is low, the interlamina fracture toughness and the intralamina one will be nearly equal at a low toughness level. However, from this result, it is found that although the intralamina fracture toughness as obtained in the previous study is high, the interlamina fracture toughness is not so high. Therefore, as for the evaluation method of the adhesion itself of the fiber/matrix interface, it may be concluded that the delamination testing method is unsuitable.

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